

The Tiv Revolts under Early Independent Nigeria, 1960-1964

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Abstract

This paper contributes in historicizing the fundamental issues leading to the Tiv political violence of 1960 – 1964. At the attainment of independence, Nigeria comprised three loosely amalgamated regions which later metamorphosed into three ethnic based political parties namely, the Northern People’s Congress (N.P.C), National Council of Nigerian and the Cameroons (N.C.N.C) and the Action Group (A.G). The main thrust of this paper is the resistance of the Tiv to the despotic leadership of the NPC with their instrument of force and the Native Administrative system. Unlike the NPC leadership, style in independent Nigeria the British system that was based on the Tiv qualities of susceptibility to realities and amenability to changes based on the Tiv popular demand. Thus, the paper uses historical approach in analyzing the Tiv Revolt of 1960 – 1964.

Introduction

After independence, the attitudes of the major political parties towards the formation of new states that could accommodate minority aspiration varied widely. The NCNC espoused self-determination for ethnic minorities. The AG also supported such movements, while the NPC steadfastly opposed separatism in the Northern Region and attempted using coercion to win over minorities in the middle belt. From 1960s, independent Nigeria became enmeshed with instances of ethnic clashes, communal conflicts as well as threats of secession from its federating units. Vasseh Godwin *et al* commented to ‘the fact that the division of the country into minorities and majorities ethnic groups encouraged sentiment sowing the seed of conflict which was

exploited by the emergent political leaders at the detriment of the center.¹

The Tiv revolt which last until 1964, started when the elected Tiv Native Authority council with a majority of United Middle Belt Congress members was dissolved by 1959, and a new one reconstituted which was totally pro-NPC. The Tor Tiv, who was the head of the Native Authority council, was coerced into supporting the NPC. This total take over happened after the United Middle Belt Congress won all the seven seats in the Tiv Division during the 1959 elections that took place in preparation for transition to independence. They presumed that if something was not done, the UMBC/AG alliance would also win the seats in the Northern House Assembly. Hence, intimidation of UMBC/AG members so

common that situation soon blew into full-scale violence. This situation led to increasing open defiance and resistance to the lawful authorities in Tivland led by the Tor Tiv. In 1964, there was an outbreak of violence leading to the destruction of lives and property. The cause of the 1964 riots arose from the attempt by the government to force the Tiv to pay a riot damaged. The imposition of arbitrary taxes within three weeks caused so much frustration and resentment among the Tiv people. Thus, the thrust of this paper is to situate the fundamental issues leading to the Tiv revolt from 1960 – 1964 within historical lens.

The Tiv Revolts of 1960s

The year 1960 remains a remarkable date in the political history of Nigeria generally. The year marked the change of political leadership from erstwhile British colonial administrators to indigenous administrators. The emergent indigenous administration was NPC controlled by virtue of the party's overall electoral victory. Right from the early stage of the Nigerian nationalist administration, visible manifestations of ineptitude regarding the administration of the Tiv people had begun to surge. Under colonial leadership the goal of administering the Tiv was successfully pursued. This colonial

administrative success was based on its qualities of susceptibility to realities and amenability to changes based on Tiv popular demand. For instance, right from the early period of the colonial administration in Tivland, it studied the Tiv people and came to appreciate that the use of force was not usually likely to achieve desired success in the administration of the people. Hence, the use of peaceful approach, tact, patience and the persuasion to reason was the administration's best option.

It could be said that the British officials administered the Tiv people with consideration for their peculiarities. It was this colonial administrative policy that accounted for the various a foretasted administrative reorganizations in Tivland culminating in the rectification of certain anomalies; and in some instances, introduction of entirely new values, but in accordance with the temperament of the Tiv people.² This positive approach, naturally rendered Tiv revolts against the administration unnecessary. This therefore explains the absence of Tiv revolts during the period of colonial administration of Tivland, notwithstanding some historian's attempt at upgrading anti-witchcraft movements of the period to revolt movements merely to justify unnecessary colonial condemnation.³

However, on the assumption of the mantle of independent leadership by the NPC regional government, this peaceful trend was severely altered. This alteration was due mainly to the attitude of the new administration. It was an opposite of the colonial administration. It was invidiously arrogant. It was untactful, impatient, insensitive to genuine popular wish of the Tiv, and generally repressive and reprobative. It did not care to study and understand prevailing issues with a view to offering appropriate amicable remedies. The administration had erroneously felt that with its sole monopoly over the instrument of coercion, everything was easily achievable. It had thought that it could even force the Tiv into submission. But, this was also to be vehemently resisted by the Tiv as could be seen below. However, it was this mentality of the NPC administration that necessitated its provocative handling of the situation surrounding the 1959 federal election that eventually culminated in Tiv revolts against the administration in the 1960s.

The ugly situation surrounding the 1959 federal election worsened after the election. The NPC government interpreted the Tiv opposition to it as an expression of anti-northern solidarity. The result of this was invariably an increased determination of the NPC government to break the Tiv

opposition. As noted earlier, and as expressed by the result of the 1959 federal election, unlike the UMBC-AG alliance, the NPC lacked popular support in Tivland. Later, the ruling party, NPC, began to view with extreme disfavor the AG's incursion into the Northern Region through the UMBC. The NPC regional government in the North therefore decided to take punitive measures to counter the ever-growing influence of the UMBC-AG alliance in Tivland. The Native Authority constituted the major weapon of the NPC regional government in the realization of this goal. It is important to note that even before the 1959 federal election, the Tor Tiv had aligned with the party in power – the NPC.⁴ Moreover, the council of ten which had emerged in 1959 following the dissolution of the Tiv Native Authority council comprised only NPC supporters as they were merely handpicked by the Tor Tiv, and were merely ratified by the clan heads by their so-called elections.⁵

Hence, the Tor Tiv, with his deputy and the NPC inclined Native Authority council kept on pressurising the Tiv into joining the NPC which was not the party of their choice. Consequently, the UMBC retaliated by making personal attacks on the Tor Tiv from the platform. They called him an NPC party agent.⁶ And as a matter of fact, the Tor Tiv was rendered

unpopular. This situation angered the Tor Tiv and his co-NPC adherent administrators who had become repressive and despotic in the pursuit of their cause. Hence, UMBC loyalists, including their wives and children were severely discriminated against in all areas. Gross witch-hunting and victimization of UMBC members became officialised as official prejudice was highly against the UMBC.⁷ Notwithstanding, the UMBC stalwarts were unbending in their opposition to the NPC. Amidst the UMBC intransigent opposition to the NPC menace, tension further became intensified.

Another source of discontent was that in the 1959 federal election campaign, the UMBC leadership had promised their followers the creation of a Middle Belt State should they vote the party into power. However, after the election, though the UMBC had won an overwhelming victory in Tiv division, their dream was to remain a mirage as the UMBC-AG alliance, in spite of their victory in the division, still remained in the minority in the overall result, and hence, could not form a government and therefore implement its manifesto.⁸ Consequently, the UMBC members interpreted this to mean a frustration of their legitimate cause by the NPC. Moreover, with the degeneration of the Native Authority to an

oppressive weapon against the UMBC, the UMBC members decided to disregard the NPC controlled administration and its orders in Tiv division.

On the other hand, the failure of the NPC in Tiv division in the 1959 federal election invariably signified the futility of the ambition of the Tiv members of the party to secure covetous appointment such as ministers in the NPC federal government, as they had nothing politically to bargain with, for such positions. The NPC members therefore saw the activities of their kins in the opposition party as tantamounting to the frustration of their progress. Their anger was accordingly sharpened against their kinsmen in the UMBC.⁹

In March, 1960 the UMBC discussed a variety of its grievances which were subsequently embodied in a petition to the premier of the North. Later in the year before the Tiv revolt of that year, Joseph S. Tarka also sent a petition to the premier regarding the unfavorable treatment which was given to his supporters. His petition described instances of victimisation of his supporters through discrimination on the basis of political beliefs. The petition which drew attention to the suffering of thousands of his supporters was intended to expose a policy of victimization and

oppression. Tarka expressed the UMBC disillusionment and lack of confidence in the Tiv Native Authority when he declared that, 'The Tiv N.A. machinery is off the rail and has completely betrayed the trust which your Government (the Northern premier's) had invested in.'¹⁰

Furthermore, he complained about the use of the Native Authority as a weapon of oppression in the hands of the clan and kindred heads and tax-collectors, mass imprisonment of UMBC supporters; the delay and rejection of appeals by UMBC supporters; the partisanship of court presidents; the denial of means of livelihood to his supporters through the closure of their markets and stores, and the refusal to give or renew their trading licenses; physical torture, including whipping tax-payers and their wives publicly. It was hoped by the petitioner that the Northern regional government would investigate the grievances laid down in the petition with a view to addressing them. But alas; the grievances were not only refused to be investigated, but rather the premier re-affirmed his confidence in the Tiv Native Authority thereby encouraging the later to continue victimizing and oppressing the UMBC supporters.¹¹

Following this response from the premier of Northern region it became clear to the UMBC that peaceful protest against the NPC influenced maladministration in Tivland was useless. The response more than ever sharpened the UMBC discontent against the administration. Hence, the UMBC members became more than ever vehement in their disobedience and opposition to the administration in Tivland. And the continued attempt to stifle stiff Tiv opposition to NPC domination and maladministration culminated in the outbreak of the violent revolt of 1960. Although a number of incidents contributed to the heightening of tension in Tivland, yet it was the incident in the Yandev area of Tivland in August, 1960 that finally sparked up the actual revolt in Tivland. The incident was consequent upon an address of Or Ako, the clan head of Yandev, to his people at a market which was legally established long ago by Mr. KumburAkapi. There were conflicting reports as to the actual content of Or Ako's speech. The official police report claimed that he spoke about tax collection. However, others, including the UMBC alleged that he was partisan in his remarks and criticized members of his clan who supported the opposition party. According to the UMBC version, Or Ako, in the process of his speech asked for silence and then declared that he forbade

the shouting of the slogan, 'Tarka', 'Awo'. Consequently, some of his listeners were alleged to have laughed at him for using such partisan expressions. Following this scornful treatment by the audience, the chief left in fury, threatening the closure of the market. On the next market day, 13 August, 1960, the chief, accompanied by some native authority policemen, ordered the people who were buying and selling in the market to disperse or face arrest. However, the policemen were driven out by the people who were already armed with dangerous weapons, including bows and arrows. Thereafter, the Tor Tiv, escorted by some policemen went to Yandev, not to settle the misunderstanding, but to enforce the order of the native authority council relating to the closure of the market. Following the intervention of the Tor Tiv in favour of the chief of Yandev, the people refused to submit to the authority of the Tor Tiv. Instead, they were determined to express their dissatisfaction by violent resistance if necessary.¹²

On 25 August, 1960, a complete anti-riot squad of the native authority police, armed with batons and shields was sent to enforce the order closing the market. However, the police had to retire in the face of a determined and fierce attack by an angry mob armed with poisoned arrows. Three

policemen were wounded. Further attempts to arrest some of the identified mob leaders were stubbornly resisted by the disaffected mob in Yandev. It was against this background of Tiv violent resistance to the indigenous maladministration by fellow Nigerians that the 1960 revolt broke out and became widespread throughout Tivland within a few days. The Tor Tiv and the administration attempted to make contact with the incensed Yandev people on the 30 August, 1960, but the later refused to yield to pressure and there was a breakdown of law and order in the Yandev area. It was from here that the revolt of the Tiv people against the oppressive administration spread like wide fire to most parts of Tivland within some few days. There was wide scale arson. The burning was particularly directed against the property of NPC supporters, the clan and kindred heads, court presidents and members, and tax collectors. At the Moslem stranger village of GidanUga in the Tiv area of Mbalagh, the village was completely burnt down by the irate Tiv. And through September to October 1960, this rage continued unabated. It is important to note that during the 1960 revolts, large scale destruction was basically directed against property rather than lives. Notwithstanding, minimal destruction of

human lives on both sides (the police and the Tiv) was also registered.¹³

Following the ferocity of the revolt activities which the police were unable to subdue during this period, most of the clan heads were forced to flee to Gboko. But due to the revolt, the Northern regional government was forced to take certain measures which included the dissolution of the highly discredited Tiv Native Authority Council. The administrative secretary to the Native Authority, Mr. Atedze who was a staunch NPC supporter, and expectedly strongly hated by the Tiv of the UMBC was also dismissed from service. Hence, the powers of the native authority council was vested in the Senior Divisional Officer.

A Tiv advisory council of twelve members was also constituted to assist the Senior Divisional Officer in his task of reconciliation and administration of the Division. Of the twelve members, the NPC, UMBC and traditional leaders, each had three representatives. The Tiv progressive union had one member and the remaining two members were Senior Administrative Officers. The dissolution of the Tiv native authority council was a welcome development to the Tiv, although this did not immediately arrest the wave of violent revolt as the measure was taken too

late. Nevertheless, some Tiv people, who themselves had been part of the revolt interpreted this dissolution as a victory and saw no justification in the continuation of the revolt, since they felt that the government had started yielding to them

Furthermore, the government decided to reform the judiciary. Previous arrangement in the clan grade D courts had been that the office of the court President was held by the clan heads. Hence, this implied the combination of both the executive powers and the judiciary powers by the clan heads. This arrangement clearly violates the accepted principle of the rule of law – that the judiciary shall be independent of the executive. There is no wonder, therefore, that this arrangement gave room for gross perversion of justice in Tivland.

Following the 1960 revolt, a new penal code was introduced and applied to the Tiv. All criminal jurisdiction (the power to imprison for six months) was taken away from, the existing clan courts and vested in sixteen new courts, one in each of the district council areas. The president of each court was to be an educated man. A provincial court of appeal was set up with a regional government employee as president.

In the general reconstruction consequent upon the revolt, the administration was

also concerned with the task of reconciling the traditional leaders with their people in their various clans. Considering the fact that the clan heads had completely fallen into their subjects' disfavor, and were subject to open attacks by the subjects, culminating in the fleeing of most of them to Gboko in the heated period of the 1960 revolts; the tasks of reinstating them in order to re-establish their authority and prestige in the various clans, thereby reestablishing effective local administration which broke down completely during the revolt became expectedly enormous.

However, with a series of reconciliatory meeting which involved representative of both the NPC and UMBC appealing to their supporters to refrain from further acts of violence and accept the authority of their chiefs, violence ceased. Hence, confidence and peace were restored and most of the clan heads were reinstated and reunited with their people, but subject to a warning from the administration that they should, in future, desist from political activities. Moreover, the Tiv advisory council proved to be very effective in the task of restoring unity to the division. It was therefore through the above process that the people's resolve to pursue the revolt further was gradually weakened,

thereby bringing the revolt to an end by the end of 1960.

Although the revolt swept across most parts of Tivland, it could not be said that it was really organized; it could be said that it was spontaneously generated as a result of the serious grudge the people held against the maladministration under the NPC regional government of Northern Nigeria. The destructive activities of the revolt, as noted was not so much in human lives as property. An official government source indicated that sixteen deaths were confirmed as being due to the revolt; four resulted from police shooting and the remainder were killed by people defending their property. A police report also put the number of those injured at eighty-three. The official figure of deaths contrast with Dent's estimate of twenty-five deaths and that of a senior police officer who put the figure at about fifty deaths and two hundred injured. Notwithstanding, this discrepancy, the figure still suggests low number of casualties considering the level of violence of the revolt.

After the revolts had died down, a large number of people were arrested, tried, convicted and sentenced to various terms of imprisonment ranging from a few strokes of the cane to ten years. The Nigeria police force reckoned that it

arrested over five thousand Tiv in connection with the revolt activities. Of these, three thousand, eight hundred and eighty two were convicted. This number was so high that new prison arrangements were made to contain such a marvelous figure. In point of fact, this was strange in Nigerian history.

After the revolt too, a commission was set up just to assess the extent of damage caused by the activities of the revolt. The Fletcher Commission, as it was known, estimated the value of damaged property at N1,011,954.00. The official intention regarding this project was to find out the figure so as to force the Tiv people into paying the estimated sum through the imposition of a punitive tax to be evenly worked out and distributed among all taxable adults. Hence, consequent upon the submission of the estimated figure, the premier, Northern Region directed that:

The sum of N1,011,954 shall be apportioned amongst and payable by every adult male tax payer resident in the area; in the financial year 1961/2 who is directed to pay tax under the Direct Taxation Ordinance, in equal proportion.¹⁴

This policy, apart from forcing the Tiv to pay reparation, was aimed at teaching them a lesson.

However, this policy was to be counterproductive as it rather sowed the seed of future discontent and troubles in the division. It became another source of frustration and was therefore a strong factor in the people's second revolt in 1964 which was worse than the previous one. Moreover, this shows clearly that the administrators in Northern Nigeria did not understand the Tiv people whom they were governing, and were not prepared to study them. This is in sharp contrast to the administration by the British colonialists.

The Second Tiv Revolt of 1964 (Atemtyo)

Although the 1960 revolt had come to an end by the end of the year, and a series of reforms and rapid reconciliation followed, it was quite clear that the fundamental issue had not been addressed but merely suppressed. This statement is justified by the resurgence of the problems which culminated in the second revolt of the people in 1964 which was more fierce than the 1960 revolt in terms of human casualty.

As noted earlier one of the measures taken after the 1960 revolt was that the Tiv should pay reparation for the estimated damage caused by the revolt. To do this, the sum of four pounds ten shillings (\$4.10) was imposed on all taxable Tiv

male adults in order to make up the figure estimated as representing the damage casued in Tivland due to the revolt.¹⁵¹⁰ Besides, they were to pay their usual; annual tax, which combined with the punitive tax pushed the sum to a little over nine pounds per person. In point of fact, this was a lot of money for a poor farmer to raise in 1960.

But those who were unable to pay the tax were subjected to torture and degrading treatment by the local police, and their property were finally confiscated and cheaply auctioned just to realise the needed amount.¹⁶ In the first instance, the Tivs did not welcome the imposition of this tax and hated the idea of paying it. Hence, in spite of this governeemt intimidation it was not an easy task having to force the Tiv people into paying the punitive tax, as they continued to frustrate such attempts with impunity. Expectedly, tension had started building up between the previous opposing forces of the UMBC and the pro-NPC administration in Tivland and the NPC members outside the administration. This obnoxious government policy was highly reprehensible and defied by the Tiv people. Hence, in spite of the human and material resources committed to the collection of the tax, much was not collected by the beginning of 1963.¹⁷ But

the Comassie Commission superficially attributed this failure to ‘Lack of cooperartion of the clan, kindred heads and the tax collectors’.¹⁸

To compound the situation some clan heads, instead of finding out why taxes were not being paid, resorted to illegal dismissal of the tax collectors. But as Makar rightly observed, ‘... the dismissal could not be and was not a revenue yielding venture’.¹⁹ Apart from the tension generated by the punitive tax policy of the government, inter party animosity had started to dangerously resurge. This is partly attributable to the Northern regional election of 1961 in which the UMBC again overwhelmingly won against the NPC; the arrest and detention of the UMBC president general, Mr. J.S. Tarka, and the general high handedness of the NPC government in dealing with the people considered to be party to the revolt of 1960.

It is a common phenomenon among the Tiv people to resort to reckless prouncements during political electioneering campaigns merely to score political points with a view to ensuring political victory against opponent parties. Songs are normally composed in the most slanderous and ridiculous language so as to provoke opponents, and in the end, achieve

the same goal. Naturally, such development is not likely to engender a peaceful atmosphere. Rather, it generates serious disharmony. This is no doubt a despicable political strategy but neither was the 1959 federal election nor that of the 1961 free from it. Thus, with the return of electioneering campaign preceding the 1961 regional election, the differences that led to the 1960 revolt had started to resurge. This resurgence led to antipathy between the UMBC and the NPC regional government. The NPC supporters outside the administration, governmental agents such as the recently restored clan heads, Tor Tiv and his deputy, the court presidents and the rest of them once again took side with the NPC regional government in the North.

Correspondingly, official prejudice became sharpened against the UMBC who constituted the majority in Tivland. In point of fact, this official prejudice was clearly exhibited in the annual report of Mallam Tanko Yusuf, the new provincial commissioner for Benue province, to the premier Northern region, regarding a contemplated district council elections in 1963. He wrote:

If elections to the District Councils, as requested by these power-drunk elements (UMBC leaders) are to be held at the moment (1963) it is definite that

the UMBC will win the majority of the seats and gain full control of the District Councils... I have therefore decided that Advisory committees are established.²⁰

Hence, this blatant display of official prejudice was accompanied by serious victimization. Tarka himself was arrested on frivolous accusation and detained shortly before the District Councils election in 1961.²¹ Moreover, the ugly treatment of the UMBC members for the 1960 revolt such as the long years of prison terms on whatever grounds, and the aforementioned punitive tax generated meaningful discontent in Tivland.

It is therefore the above factors that accounted for the return of the revolting situation in Tivland which finally culminated in the outbreak of the second Tiv revolt in 1964. It is in accordance with this contention that Martin Dent, the District officer, Tiv Division, at the time of the 1960 revolt later wrote:

Slowly the suspicion and tension that led to the 1960 outbreak reappeared. The all-party Advisory Committee which had done such good work fell into disuse by the end of 1962... the sole Native Authority lost the cooperation of the Native Authority staff who became irresponsible and ill-disciplined. There were fears that the NPC was trying to force its way back by use of the same methods – the victimization of Native Authority staff, the arrests

and intimidation of opponents and the dismissal of tax-collectors. The UMBC was able to point with some justification to NPC attempts to dominate the new provincial council for Benue and the Tiv Advisory Council. Relations deteriorated till there was talk of Wanchancha, the broom that was to sweep all the NPC from the divisions.²²

It is very clear from the foregoing that the atmosphere in Tivland was so tense by 1963 that a mere spark could easily blow up another revolt.

This issue that finally precipitated the 1964 revolt was an incident in the Mbalagh clan of Tombo area in Tivland. This incident was the killing, in February, of Gbargbar Apinega, the clan head of Mbalagh, and three others. It is alleged that Gbargbar was wicked and staunch NPC sympathiser who had a private cell in his compound where he indiscriminately and arbitrarily detained his opponents.²³ But alas his subjects, probably, of the UMBC reacted against his vile treatment of their clan members by attacking and killing him on the 12th February, 1964. It was this action that ushered in the second Tiv revolt in 1964 which is popularly known in Tiv language as atemtyo(head-smashing) – so named because it was marked by the Tiv smashing to death, the heads of their Tiv NPC supporters whom they referred to as

baja a Tiv derogatory word for, or reference to the Hausa.

Following the murder of Gbargbar Apinega a free-for-all fight ensued between the supporters and opponents of the clan head. To suppress the Mbalagh incident a detachment of the Nigeria police was quickly drafted to the scene. On their way, however, they were ambushed by an armed group of irate Tiv. In the ensuing confrontation, six Nigeria policemen were reported killed and several seriously wounded; others were reported missing.²⁴

What followed this development was the rapid and spontaneous reaction of the people against the authorities in most parts of Tivland and the glaring inability of the Nigeria police to contain the chaotic situation. Amidst the helplessness of the police, administrative activities were completely paralysed. It could be deduced from the foregoing analysis that the nature of the issues of the 1960s were not the same as those of the anti-witchcraft movements that intermittently beset Tiv society in the pre-colonial and colonial periods. By the standard of the political concepts of revolt, we would submit that the issues of the 1960s represent a more ideal picture of revolt situation while those of the pre-colonial and colonial periods do not.

Northern Nigeria's Official Reaction to Tiv Revolts of 1964

Following the 1964 revolts, the government of Northern Nigeria appointed, in March 1964, a commission of inquiry to look into the Tiv question. The government directed the commission which was known as the Coomassie Commission²⁵ of inquiry to investigate the unrest in Tiv Division since 1960 and '... to examine its background; and to recommend a system of local Government that will be capable of providing the services required of it as well as command the support and loyalty of the Tiv people'.²⁶

The report of this commission was submitted to the government on the 23 July, 1964. But because it was too critical of the administration, the report was never published.²⁷ ²² However, the government issued a white paper, summarising the Commission's findings and recommendations. Notwithstanding the sketchy nature of the white paper, it helped in showing, among other things, that post independence Nigerian government had no proper knowledge of the Tiv people who were part of the Nigerian federation, due to erroneous opinion that it could force the Tiv into an obedient and docile position. The government was very untactful and

uncompromising in its pursuit of this objective.

But as the case has been shown, the intimidating posture of the administration did not achieve its desire of forcing the Tiv into submission. Rather, the people resorted to violent revolt against the administration. Consequently, the administration was forced into taking a reasonable approach of investigating into the continued unrest in Tivland.

By the content of the report, it was clear that the grievances of the Tiv were genuine. And in some instances, the Commission outrightly condemned the administration in Tivland. For instance, according to the white paper:

The Commission found the condition of the administration even worse than had been reported. Many of the staff showed little interest in their work and spent much of their time on personal pursuits, such as politics and trading. Moral was low, and discipline bad. They tended to be oppressive. Self-seeking and irresponsible and to resent any measure of control. The situation in the rural areas was even worse.²⁸

Similarly it noted: 'Those in authority did not behave with tact and that party politics was brought into the sphere of administration'.²⁹ In its recommendations, the commission noted among other things that, 'Emphasis must be placed on

diffuseness of power and decentralization and the system of local Government must accord as far as possible with the indigenous social structure'.³⁰

Furthermore, it submitted that the NPC government should recognise the existence and strength of the opposition (the UMBC-AG) in Tiv Division, by giving the party an opportunity to share in the running of local affairs. Although the Coomassie Commission carried out its assignment successfully and its work could be seen as a useful contribution to the understanding of the Tiv question, yet it has its own serious shortcomings. For instance, the Commission conclusively made some weird declarations regarding the Tiv, among which was that, 'The Tiv resent authority and persons holding authority. So any party in power is liable to lose its support; when in opposition it is likely to gain support'.³¹

This statement is untrue. This is because it creates the impression that it is in the character of the Tiv to just resent authority. But this is not the case. In short, mere time has proved its falsehood as the Tiv people were solidly in support of the National party of Nigeria, led in Tivland, by the same J.S. Tarka of the UMBC in the 1950s and 60s, and at the national level, by the former President Shehu Shagari, during the

defunct second Republic which lasted for over four years without Tiv revolt. This mere fact therefore renders further arguments on this point unnecessary. Suffice it to conclude that the problem derived from the unberable maladministration of indigenous administrators as shown by our analysis above. Such glaring maladministration was not found in the colonial era; hence the absence of Tiv revolts during that period.

Another area of serious inaccurate assessment by the Commission was its inability to distinguish the Tiv revolts of the 1960s from the Tiv intra-cultural conflicts which occurred in the colonial period. For, it described both types of Tiv disturbances as being the same, '... an uprising which is basically a violent reaction against authority and abuse of power ... the Haakaa and Nyambua disturbances and those of 1960 and 1964 were of this type'.³² Indeed this is an inaccurate conclusion; nevertheless, the mix-up in the nature of the distinctiveness of the phenomena has been shown above.

Although the government white paper on the Coomassie Commission of inquiry had stated a lot more than has been mentioned here, yet the essence here is not to encumber ourselves with all details of the white paper, but to relevantly x-ray it, to

the extent that it concerns the focus of this study. Generally, the work of the Commission was welcomed in Tivland. Previously, unacceptable concessions were granted to the Tiv by the Commission, though there was not to be the creation of the long agitated for, Middle Belt State; and the unsolved problem of the status of Makurdi township administration still remained. Notwithstanding the acceptability of the recommendations of this commission, the full implementation of the recommendations was not to be, as the military took over the administration of Nigeria.

Conclusion

It would be reasonable to conclude that under the military government, the position of the Tiv was not as it had been in the administration of the First Republic. There was a considerable improvement in the destiny of the people. The creation of states took place under the military government and the people found themselves in a geo-political entity – Benue Plateau state, which was even far smaller than the Middle Belt state, which they had unreservedly agitated for, over a very long period. With this improvement, Tiv revolts died a natural death. Hence, the poverty of the thesis of inherent Tiv resentment of authority and the people holding authority.

Endnotes

¹ According to V. Godwin, a seasoned Tiv scholar, it is reasonable to think that Tor Tiv decided to align with the party in power basically because he wanted to safeguard his position. This is because at appointment to the position the Tor Tiv becomes more or less a government employee. Hence, to fall into disfavour with the government was not a pleasant temptation.

² T. Abeghe, The Tiv and Tiv Riot. P.43.

³ Ibid., p.41.

⁴ Ibid., p.41.

⁵ R. Anifowose, Violence and Politics in Nigeria ..., pp.98-99.

⁶ T. Makar, The History of Political Change..., p.222.

⁷ Ibid., p.222.

⁸ R. Anifowose, Violence and Politics in Nigeria ..., p.143. For details of the 1960 revolt, this work depends primarily on this Secondary source.

⁹ Ibid., p.124.

¹⁰ M. Jibo, Tiv Politics Since 1959, (Zaria. A.B.U. Press, 1933), p.6.

¹¹ Ibid p.6.

¹² Ibid p.6.

¹³ Ibid 5-8.

¹⁴ Ibid., p.6.

¹⁵ T. Makar, The History of Political Change..., p.232.

¹⁶ A White Paper on the Government's Policy ..., cited in Ibid., p.232.

¹⁷ Ibid., p.232.

¹⁸ Malam Tanko Yusuf, Benue Provincial Commissioner, in his Annual Report to the Premier, Northern Region, cited in R. Anifowose, Violence and Politics in Nigeria ..., p.129.

¹⁹ Ibid p.129.

²⁰ M. Dent, cited in R. Anifowose, Violence and Politics in Nigeria ..., p.130.

²¹ Ibid., p.131.

²² Ibid., p.131.

²³ The Commission was known after the name of its chairman, M. Ahmadu Coomassie, C.O.N., O.B.E., Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Economic Planning. It had three other members, namely Mr. Peter Achimugu, O.B.E., Court President, Kabba Provincial Court; Mr. J.A. Reynolds, Deputy Permanent Secretary, Special Duties, Ministry for Local Government; and Mr. S.B. Daniyan (the Commission's Secretary), Acting Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Justice.

²⁴ A White Paper on the Government's Policy ..., P.I.

²⁵ Ibid., p.7.

²⁶ Ibid., p.12.

²⁷ Ibid., pp.11-12.

²⁸ Ibid., p.11,

²⁹ Ibid., p.12,

³⁰ Ibid., p.11,

³¹ Ibid., p.12

³² For instance, even until now we still hear cases of marginalisation, victimisation and the sort.